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Beat Tracking with Autoencoders

Matthew Greenlees

Supervisor: Aggelos Gkiokas

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Motivation	2
1.3	Organisation	3
2	State of the Art	4
2.1	Long short-term memory	4
2.2	Autoencoders	7
2.3	Beat tracking	10
3	Methodology	13
3.1	Preprocessing	13
3.2	Beat tracking network	18
3.3	Autoencoder	20
3.4	Experiment	21
4	Evaluation	24
4.1	F -measure	24
4.2	Continuity-based evaluation	25
4.3	Test Loss	26
4.4	Datasets	26
5	Results	28
5.1	Reference beat tracking network	28

5.2	Encoding size	30
5.3	Adding linear layers	31
5.4	Activation functions	31
5.5	Batch normalisation	32
5.6	Training with large datasets	32
6	Conclusion	35
6.1	Discussion	35
6.2	Future work	36
	List of Figures	37
	List of Tables	38
	Bibliography	39

Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my dearest friend, Macy. Without your support, love and affection these last few months, I couldn't have completed this work.

Thank you.

Acknowledgement

I would like to begin by thanking my supervisor Aggelos for his immense guidance throughout this thesis.

I also want to thank my parents for their support for the past two years, as well as their constant nagging, pushing me to finish this.

Finally, I would like to thank the cafeteria in campus del Poblenou. Your one euro coffees were vital to my education.

Abstract

This work is a study into the effectiveness of autoencoders applied to beat tracking. We propose an autoencoder architecture based on a state-of-the-art beat tracking network, the purpose of which is to create a new set of features for the beat tracking network to be trained on. The autoencoder is trained on Mel spectrograms extracted from pieces of music. After training, we pass the Mel spectrograms through the encoder half of the autoencoder only, and use the output as a new set of features. The new set of features is then used to train a beat tracking system, the results of which are compared with a reference beat tracking system trained on the Mel spectrograms. The aim of using autoencoders is to perform feature fusion on the input, resulting in an efficient encoding of the input to reduce its dimensionality, which should allow for an increase in performance when using this encoding to train the beat tracking system. Our testing showed on par performance with the reference system when using the test loss of the beat activation function as our evaluation metric, and a slight increase in performance when using more typical beat tracking evaluation metrics, such as the F -measure and continuity based metrics.

Keywords: Beat tracking; Autoencoder; Long short-term memory

Chapter 1

Introduction

Ask a human to tap along to a piece of music, and for the most part they will perform the task reasonably well. Ask a computer to perform the same task, and it will struggle. *Beat tracking* is the task of automatically labelling the positions of beats within a stream of audio, and this thesis aims to investigate whether using autoencoders can improve the performance of a state-of-the-art beat tracking algorithm.

1.1 Background

While most of the mathematics behind machine learning could be thrown up on a blackboard decades ago, it wasn't until recently that we've started to see its power realised. With the explosion in computational power and the availability of increasingly large datasets, the results achieved by machine learning have been phenomenal, leading to advancements in many fields.

One area that has benefited immensely from the boom in machine learning research is the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR), an interdisciplinary field that aims to extract information from various music formats. Tasks involved in MIR include automatic music transcription, chord estimation, source separation, acoustic scene classification and - importantly - beat tracking, the focus of this thesis.

Beat tracking has been an active area of research for decades, and has recently seen improvements in the state-of-the-art performance thanks to machine learning. This thesis looks to add to that field of research by investigating a machine learning technique which has so far not been applied to beat tracking - the use of autoencoders to create new features.

1.2 Motivation

Other than the fact that this is an interesting problem to solve from a purely academic perspective, it also has real world applications. From DJ to music production tools in the commercial sector, and automatic music transcription in the academic sector, there is plenty of value in expanding the state-of-the-art.

For machine learning techniques to be successful, they often need to be trained on large amounts of data, and this can be seen as a problem in the beat tracking community. As the locations of beats have to be individually labelled for each piece of music by an expert, and then verified by others, there are only a handful of fully labelled datasets for training beat tracking systems. It may be the case that by creating more annotated datasets, we can increase the performance of beat tracking systems, but in this thesis we propose another method that does not require more labelled datasets.

Autoencoders are an unsupervised form of machine learning, which means that they can be trained on unlabelled datasets. As a result, we can take advantage of the vast amount of unlabelled data. For instance, Srivastava et al. [1], trained an autoencoder on 300 hours of unlabelled YouTube videos to improve the performance of a classification task, yielding large improvements even when using only a small labelled dataset. Given the huge amount of unlabelled musical data available, it should be possible to improve the performance of beat tracking systems using an autoencoder. Within the field of MIR, Chandna et al. had success using an autoencoder to perform audio source separation.

1.3 Organisation

The remainder of the thesis is structured as follows.

- We begin with a recap of important topics and a discussion of the state of the art (chapter 2).
- This is followed by a detailed explanation of the autoencoder architecture proposed and the methodology used (chapter 3).
- Then, we give an explanation of how we will evaluate the results (chapter 4).
- Next is a report and discussion of the results collected (chapter 5).
- Finally, we list the contributions of the thesis and propose areas of future work (chapter 6).

Chapter 2

State of the Art

We use this chapter to discuss three fields of study. The first is that of long short-term memory networks (LSTMs). Next, we revise autoencoders. Finally, a build up of the theory and techniques of beat tracking is presented to the reader. Throughout the chapter, we assume some familiarity with neural networks.

2.1 Long short-term memory

Long short-term memory networks cannot be introduced without first presenting a discussion on recurrent neural networks (RNNs).

RNNs were originally designed to deal with sequential data, as standard neural networks struggle to capture how data changes throughout time. They can be thought of as neural networks with loops, where the output h_t at time t depends on the input x_t , as well as the outputs $h_{t-1}, h_{t-2}, \dots, h_0$ of the previous inputs in the sequence. A visual explanation of this is shown in figure 1, where A represents some neural network.

It is difficult to visualise networks with cycles in them, so they are often shown in their unrolled forms. This is shown in figure 2, where x_0, x_1, \dots, x_t represent the inputs and h_0, h_1, \dots, h_t represent the outputs at each point in time. It is important to note that all of the blocks A represent the same neural network with the same

Figure 1: A rolled RNN.

weights. This unfolding is also done in practice, so that it is possible to train the network using backpropagation.

Figure 2: An unrolled RNN.

Whilst RNNs have been effective in modelling sequential data, they are not without their problems. In 1994, Bengio et al. [2] demonstrated the difficulties RNNs encounter when trying to learn long-term dependencies. Further, in 1991, Hochreiter [3] showed that training RNNs with backpropagation can cause the gradient to either vanish or explode exponentially, making it difficult to train.

This investigation led Hochreiter and Schmidhuber [4] to introduce LSTMs in 1997, a special kind of RNN that were designed to overcome the problem of vanishing gradient, but also allowed for long-term dependencies.

In 1999, Gers, Schmidhuber and Cummins [5] identified a weakness with the standard LSTM, where sequences that are broken into sub-sequences may make it difficult for the LSTM to properly learn. To remedy this, they introduced a *forget gate* into the LSTM, a component that allows the LSTM to reset itself where necessary.

LSTMs follow a similar structure to that of the unrolled RNN in figure 2, but where the A block in a standard RNN might just be a simple activation function, LSTMs have a slightly more complicated network block, as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: The insides of an LSTM node.

In figure 3, the x and $+$ symbols represent point-wise vector multiplication and addition, converging lines represent vector concatenation and the diverging lines represent two copies of the vector. The functions in square blocks represent the sigmoid and hyperbolic tangent functions, both of which are common activation

functions. The sigmoid function is given by

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.1)$$

and the hyperbolic tangent function is given by

$$\tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}. \quad (2.2)$$

Roughly speaking, there are two flows of information. The top flow of information in figure 3 can be thought of as the long-term memory, where information can pass through the network without changing significantly. The flow at the bottom of figure 3 can be thought of as the short-term memory, which can change heavily depending on the input x_t .

One useful improvement to the standard LSTM is the bidirectional LSTM (BLSTM). Whilst a standard LSTM can look to the past for information, a BLSTM can look forward in time for information. This small addition doubles the size of the input, but makes a network more aware of context than the standard LSTM.

2.2 Autoencoders

The curse of dimensionality is a problem in machine learning where the performance of algorithms degrades as the number of variables increases. One way to deal with this is dimensionality reduction, where you somehow reduce the number of variables in the input. There are a number of different approaches that fall under the umbrella of dimensionality reduction, one of which is a technique known as *feature fusion*. The idea behind feature fusion is that variables often don't offer much use on their own, but when combined with other variables can offer useful information. This is the central idea behind autoencoders.

An autoencoder is simply a neural network with a symmetrical structure, which is trained to map its input on to its output. They were first introduced by Ballard [6] in

1987 (then known as autoassociative networks) as a means to pre-train networks, and have since been widely adopted to perform denoising and dimensionality reduction.

All autoencoders have the same similar structure, shown in figure 4, where the input \mathbf{x} is mapped by an encoder f into some encoding \mathbf{y} , which is then mapped to a reconstruction \mathbf{r} by a decoder g . As we are trying to reconstruct the input, both \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{r} have the same dimensionality, but \mathbf{y} can be larger or smaller than the input.

To compare the reconstruction against the input, we use a loss function

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, (g \circ f)(\mathbf{x})).$$

A loss function that is often used to train autoencoders is the mean squared error (MSE) function, given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2, \quad (2.3)$$

where

$$\|\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2.$$

Figure 4: All autoencoders have a similar structure.

We classify autoencoders based on their network structure. Autoencoders whose encoding has greater dimensionality than the input are known as overcomplete, whilst autoencoders whose encoding has lower dimensionality than the input are known as undercomplete. Furthermore, autoencoders with only one hidden layer are known as shallow, whilst autoencoders with more than one hidden layer are known as deep.

As we are looking to perform some form of dimensionality reduction on the data, it would make sense that we would only be interested in undercomplete autoencoders

to force an efficient representation of the data. Overcomplete autoencoders are also useful, though they require additional restraints during training.

The sigmoid function defined in equation (2.1) and the hyperbolic tangent function defined in equation (2.2) are both examples of activation functions that are often used in autoencoders. Interestingly, the rectified linear unit (ReLU) function, that has seen success in other machine learning models, doesn't work particularly well in autoencoders. The ReLU function is defined by

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(x, 0),$$

but due to the fact that it always returns zero for negative inputs, decoders tend to struggle reconstructing the inputs from the encoding. However, there is a related function called the scaled exponential linear unit (SELU), which has many of the advantages of the ReLU function, but not this drawback. As a result, the SELU activation function is well suited to training autoencoders. It is defined as

$$\text{SELU}(x) = \lambda \begin{cases} \alpha e^x - \alpha & x \leq 0 \\ x & x > 0 \end{cases}$$

where $\lambda \approx 1.05$ and $\alpha \approx 1.67$ are pre-defined constants. Kuchaiev and Ginsburg [7] found that using the SELU activation function greatly improved the performance of their deep autoencoder, which was used for a classification task.

Standard autoencoders that are solely made up of fully connected linear layers are not particularly good at reconstructing sequences. To remedy this, we can add LSTM layers to the autoencoder to help them learn sequences. In 2015, Srivastava et al [1] proposed the use of LSTM autoencoders to learn efficient representations of video sequences. In their paper, they looked at different types of decoders for different tasks, including predicting future frames. The input was fed into a single encoder, followed by two decoders, the first of which tried to reconstruct the current frame, whilst the other tried to predict future frames. They then took the encoder and fine tuned it for a classification task, to see if the representation learned in the

unsupervised learning task could improve the performance of the supervised learning task. They found that using the representation learned by the LSTM autoencoder as input improved the performance of the supervised learning task, even when they only trained the supervised model on a small number of labelled samples. They also found an improvement in performance when they trained the autoencoder on unrelated videos.

Training autoencoders involves minimising the loss calculated between the input and the reconstruction. As a result, there is no need for labelled data, and we can take advantage of potentially massive sets of unlabelled data. For example, in [1], the authors trained their autoencoder on 300 hours of unrelated YouTube videos, but found an increase in performance when they took the representations learned and used them with labelled data.

2.3 Beat tracking

We can now start looking at the state-of-the-art in beat tracking, but we begin by looking at a few necessary concepts.

Korzeniowski et al. [8] described *beat tracking* as the task of locating and labelling beats within an audio stream of music. Humans are naturally able to do this, but for computers this is no easy feat.

A *beat activation function* (BAF) is a probability function that takes as input a stream of audio and outputs the probability that a particular time instant contains a beat. This will form the basis of many of the following methods.

Traditional methods of beat tracking are usually built on top of onset detection techniques. For example, Goto and Muraoka [9] proposed a real-time beat tracking system in 1995 that used onset detection, as well as a drum sound finder, to find the location of beats within popular music in an online fashion. However, we will focus primarily on machine learning based methods, as they are the state-of-the-art.

In 2017 [10], Gkiokas and Katsouros proposed the use of convolutional neural net-

works (CNNs) trained on spectrograms in order to learn a beat activation function, the output of which was then fed into a dynamic programming algorithm. The motivation to use CNNs was that the authors intended to put the model on a small robot that would dance in time with real music. The speed of CNNs, coupled with the fact that they were only using the previous frame, meant that the algorithm worked in an online fashion. To account for beats being mislabelled in the training set, the authors used Gaussian noise around the beat locations for the target BAF.

One problem with beat tracking is the shortage of available labelled data, which requires someone to go through and individually mark all the beats in a piece of audio. Not only is this time consuming, but there's the possibility of people mislabelling the location of the beat. To remedy this, Böck et al. [11] proposed the use of multi-task learning for both tempo estimation and beat tracking. The two tasks are highly related, allowing them to learn a shared representation using CNNs. The method proposed allows the authors to take advantage of the fact that there is a lot more tempo annotated data than there is data annotated for beat tracking.

In [8], Korzeniowski et al. present a probabilistic method to approximate a BAF. The model consists of three layers of 25 BLSTM units, the last of which feeds into a single sigmoid neuron. The input of this model consists of the magnitude spectra alongside their first order difference between frames.

In 2011, Böck and Schedl [12] presented a method that is based on BLSTMs. It first transforms the audio into the frequency domain using three STFTs with different window lengths. The first order differences of these frames are then computed and, along with the frames, are used as input for the BLSTM. The BLSTM then produces a beat activation function, which is then passed to a peak detection phase. The authors then propose two different peak detection algorithms, one which aims to figure out tracks with a constant tempo, and one which aims to figure out tracks with tempo changes. This was a follow on from work by the same authors [13], the aim of which was to introduce a method of onset detection that generalised to all types of music, as opposed to being specialised to one type of music. It followed a similar model based on the first order differences of magnitude spectrums.

Following on from [12], Böck et al. [14] extended their earlier work by using a multi-model approach. To do this, they trained a network consisting of N networks followed by a model switch, which picks the most appropriate models output depending on the input.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, we will discuss the outline of the experiment, including the pre-processing of the data, the reference beat tracking network we use, the general structure of the autoencoder we use, and the experiment itself. Throughout this section, we have written everything in a manner that is clear and accessible, and detailed the experiment such that it is as reproducible as possible.

3.1 Preprocessing

The datasets used contain recordings of pieces of music and text files containing the locations of the beats in the file, which have been labelled by hand. Before running any experiments, we did some preprocessing of both the audio and the text files. For each piece of audio, we extracted three Mel-spectrograms using three different window sizes, and for each of the text files we extracted BAFs.

We begin by downsampling all the audio files to 22.05 kHz and ensuring that they are single channel, which is done by taking the average of all of the channels. Thus, for each song we have a vector \mathbf{x}_{raw} representing the audio, with a sampling rate of $f_s = 22050$. The audio is then normalised to a vector \mathbf{x} , where

$$\mathbf{x} = \frac{9}{10} \frac{\mathbf{x}_{\text{raw}}}{\max(\mathbf{x}_{\text{raw}})}.$$

The next step is to compute three short-time Fourier transforms X_W of \mathbf{x} using window sizes $W \in \{1024, 2048, 4096\}$. This is computed as

$$X_W(n, k) = \sum_{l=\frac{W}{2}}^{\frac{W}{2}-1} w(l) \cdot \mathbf{x}(l + nh) \cdot e^{-\frac{2\pi i l k}{W}}$$

for $0 \leq k \leq W - 1$, where k is the frequency bin index, n is the frame index, h is the hop size, and w is the Hann window, defined as

$$w(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{W - 1} \right) \right]$$

for $0 \leq x \leq W - 1$. For our purposes, we use the same hop size of $h = 220$ for all the window sizes, resulting in the same number of frames N_F for each W . Thus, X_W is a $N_F \times W$ matrix.

Next, we compute the magnitude spectra S_W by taking the absolute value $|X_W|$ of X_W and discarding the mirrored part of the spectra, so frames of length W become length $W_{\text{mag}} = \frac{W}{2} + 1$, and so S_W is a $N_F \times W_{\text{mag}}$ matrix.

To extract the Mel-spectrogram from the magnitude spectra, we need to create a filter bank F of $N_{\text{mel}} = 40$ triangular filters evenly spaced on the Mel scale. To convert between Mel and Hz, we use

$$\text{freqToMel}(x) = 1127.01048 \ln \left(1 + \frac{x}{700} \right)$$

and its inverse

$$\text{melToFreq}(x) = 700 \exp \left(\frac{x}{1127.01048} - 1 \right).$$

To create the filter bank, we supply a minimum frequency f_{min} and a maximum frequency f_{max} , which in our case are $f_{\text{min}} = 1$ and $f_{\text{max}} = \frac{f_s}{2} = 11,025$, and then map these to their corresponding Mel values using the equations above, so $m_{\text{min}} = \text{freqToMel}(f_{\text{min}})$ and $m_{\text{max}} = \text{freqToMel}(f_{\text{max}})$. Then we can use these to

create the list of equally spaced points

$$\mathbf{u} = m_{\min} + \frac{m_{\max} - m_{\min}}{N_{\text{mel}} + 1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ N_{\text{mel}} + 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

containing the N_{mel} peaks of the triangular filters and the two endpoints. This vector is then mapped to a vector \mathbf{u} containing the corresponding values in Hz, where $\mathbf{v} = \text{melToFreq}(\mathbf{u})$, from which we can then get the frequency bin positions \mathbf{a} with

$$\mathbf{a} = \left\lfloor \frac{W_{\text{mag}}}{f_s} \mathbf{v} \right\rfloor.$$

Finally, we can use these frequency bin positions to construct a filter bank F , where

$$F(k, m) = \begin{cases} 0 & k < \mathbf{a}_{m-1}, \\ \frac{k - \mathbf{a}_{m-1}}{\mathbf{a}_m - \mathbf{a}_{m-1}} & \mathbf{a}_{m-1} \leq k < \mathbf{a}_m, \\ 1 & k = \mathbf{a}_m, \\ \frac{\mathbf{a}_{m+1} - k}{\mathbf{a}_{m+1} - \mathbf{a}_m} & \mathbf{a}_m < k \leq \mathbf{a}_{m+1}, \\ 0 & k > \mathbf{a}_{m+1}. \end{cases}$$

We now have F , a $W_{\text{mag}} \times N_{\text{mel}}$ matrix, which we multiply with S_W , a $N_F \times W_{\text{mag}}$ matrix, to get a $N_F \times N_{\text{mel}}$ matrix. We then add one to each element of the matrix and take its log to get

$$M_W(n, m) = \log_{10}(S_W F + 1)$$

for each W .

The final step in this construction is to take the first order differences between the frames D_W , and concatenate the matrices for the three different window sizes together, where

$$D_W(n, m) = \begin{cases} 0 & n = 0, 0 \leq m < N_{\text{mel}}, \\ M_W(n, m) - M_W(n - 1, m) & 1 \leq n < N_F, 0 \leq m < N_{\text{mel}} \end{cases}$$

for each W . The inputs to our beat tracking network X can then be constructed as

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} D_{1024} & D_{2048} & D_{4096} \end{bmatrix},$$

which is a $N_F \times 3N_{\text{mel}}$ matrix. Note that this is only for one piece of audio, and we need to do this for every piece in the dataset.

Now we can detail the construction of the BAF. For each piece of audio, we take the corresponding text file and extract the beat locations to create a set $B = \{b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{n-1}\}$ of beat locations. We then create a vector of times

$$T = \frac{h}{f_s} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ N_{\text{frames}} - 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

representing the time at the beginning of each frame, which we then use to create a set

$$D = \{\arg \min |b - T| : b \in B\},$$

of indices representing frames containing a beat, where $\arg \min$ gives the index minimising $|b - T|$. With this, we can create a vector of impulses representing the location of the beats with $\mathbf{i} = [i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{N-1}]$, where

$$i_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } j \in D, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Now, we do not just pass a vector of impulses to the model, as the network would struggle to learn anything from it. Instead, we need to smooth the impulses to turn

it into a BAF. The two types of smoothing that we use are square and constant.

The idea behind constant smoothing is to replace a constant number of frames around a beat location with 1's. Given a smoothing factor s_f and the indices of frames with a beat $D = \{d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{n-1}\}$, we can construct a BAF

$$\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 \\ y_1 \\ \vdots \\ y_{N-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

as

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in \text{locations,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$, where

$$\text{locations} = \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} \{x \in \mathbb{Z} : d_i - s_f \leq x \leq d_i + s_f\}.$$

The process of creating a BAF with square smoothing is slightly more involved, as the idea behind it is to replace the frames around a beat with 1's, where the number of frames changed before and after a beat depend on the distance between the beat and the closest beats either side of it. Like constant smoothing, it requires a smoothing factor s_f .

Concretely, given a smoothing factor s_f and the indices of frames with a beat D , we create two numbers, neg_i and pos_i for each $i = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$, which represent the number of frames each side of the beat we will replace with 1's. These are computed as

$$\text{neg}_i = \max\left(3, \left\lfloor \frac{d_i - d_{i-1}}{s_f} \right\rfloor\right)$$

and

$$\text{pos}_i = \max\left(3, \left\lfloor \frac{d_{i+1} - d_i}{s_f} \right\rfloor\right),$$

where we always have at least three frames either side of a beat to contain 1's. With

these, we can create a BAF \mathbf{y} with

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in \text{locations,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$, where

$$\text{locations} = \bigcup_{i=0}^{n-1} \{x \in \mathbb{Z} : d_i - \text{neg}_i \leq x \leq d_i + \text{pos}_i\}.$$

In practice, the impulse vectors are saved down during pre-processing, and then calculated in-memory during training. This is so that we can easily experiment with the type of smoothing as well as the smoothing factor s_f . Another implementation detail is that our model will output a matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y} & 1 - \mathbf{y} \end{bmatrix}$$

representing the classes of frames with a beat and frames without a beat. During training, $1 - \mathbf{y}$ will be calculated in-memory, so there is no need to save it down during pre-processing.

3.2 Beat tracking network

The beat tracking model used is based on a state-of-the-art network introduced by Böck [12]. The network takes the inputs X calculated above, and outputs an estimated BAF $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$. During training, it compares this output $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ with the ground truth \mathbf{y} using the binary cross-entropy loss function given by

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N [y_n \log(\hat{y}_n) + (1 - y_n) \log(1 - \hat{y}_n)]. \quad (3.1)$$

During training, the inputs X are split into batches, the size of which can be configured, and fed into the model. The model itself is a linear sequence of layers, each fed into the next, shown in figure 5.

The first layer in the network is a batch normalisation layer. Batch normalisation attempts to aide the training of models by normalising the distribution of the inputs and outputs of layers, which vary as parameters change. It does this by subtracting the mean of the batch from each element in the batch, then dividing each element by the standard deviation of the batch. This technique was introduced by Ioffe and Szegedy in 2015, and is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_B - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_B]}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[\mathbf{x}_B] + \epsilon}} * \gamma + \beta,$$

where \mathbf{x}_B is the batch data, $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_B]$ is the mean of \mathbf{x}_B , $\text{Var}[\mathbf{x}_B]$ is the variance of \mathbf{x}_B , ϵ is some small positive number, $*$ is point-wise multiplication, and γ and β are learnable parameter vectors of size \mathbf{x}_B . Each batch normalisation layer adds more parameters to be learned, but this is a trade off for faster learning.

The output of this layer is then fed into a sequence of N_{LSTM} BLSTM layers, where $N_{\text{LSTM}} \geq 1$, followed by another batch normalisation layer. After this, the output is fed into N_{Linear} fully connected linear layers, where $N_{\text{Linear}} \geq 1$. The final layer is another fully connected linear layer with two nodes, representing the classes of beat and no beat. These layers use the softmax activation function to map each element of the final layer to the range $(0, 1)$, and so that their sum is always 1. For a vector \mathbf{x} , the softmax of each element x_i of \mathbf{x} is given by

$$\text{softmax}(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_j e^{x_j}}.$$

We use the softmax activation function to ensure that our output BAF represents a probability function. Once we have calculated the output of our model, we are able to calculate the loss using the binary cross-entropy function and backpropagate the errors. Finally, the model is trained with stochastic gradient descent.

The output of the model is a BAF, so for each frame gives a value between zero and one. To get the locations of the beats, we pass the output of our model to a dynamic programming algorithm proposed by Krebs et al. in 2015 [15]. However, we will focus primarily on the output BAF throughout this thesis.

Figure 5: The structure of the beat tracking network used.

3.3 Autoencoder

We propose an autoencoder based on the same state-of-the-art beat tracking network by Böck [12], as discussed in the previous section. The autoencoder

$$A = A_{\text{dec}} \circ A_{\text{enc}}$$

consists of an encoder A_{enc} and a decoder A_{dec} . The encoder takes as input the features X described in section 3.1 and outputs some encoding R . The decoder then takes the encoding R as input and tries to reconstruct X from it, returning as output an estimation \hat{X} . During training, the MSE loss function defined in (2.3) is used to find the error between X and \hat{X} . Just like the beat tracking network, the autoencoder is trained using stochastic gradient descent.

The encoder follows a similar layout to the beat tracking network we are using. It consists of a single batch normalisation layer, followed by an LSTM encoder, which is simply a set of BLSTM layers. This is then fed into another batch normalisation layer and then into a linear encoder, which itself is just a set of fully connected linear layers. The output of the linear encoder is the encoding R that we are hoping is some efficient representation of the input X . Similarly, the decoder follows a layout based on the beat tracking network. The decoder takes as input the encoding R and passes it to an LSTM decoder, which is simply a series of BLSTM layers. The output of the LSTM decoder is then fed as input to a final batch normalisation layer, followed by a linear decoder, which is simply a series of fully connected linear layers, the output of which is our estimation \hat{X} . An overview of the autoencoder used is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: The structure of the autoencoder used.

3.4 Experiment

This thesis seeks to answer the question *can we use autoencoders to improve the performance of a state-of-the-art beat tracking system?* To do this, we propose the following methodology.

1. Train a beat tracking system B_{Ref} on a training set

$$X_1^{\text{train}}, X_2^{\text{train}}, \dots, X_N^{\text{train}}$$

with corresponding targets

$$\mathbf{y}_1^{\text{train}}, \mathbf{y}_2^{\text{train}}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N^{\text{train}}.$$

This will be our reference beat tracking system.

2. Use the trained beat tracking system to calculate the estimated BAFs

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_1^{\text{test}}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_2^{\text{test}}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_N^{\text{test}}$$

from the test set.

3. Train the autoencoder A on a dataset

$$X_1^*, X_2^*, \dots, X_N^*,$$

which may be the same dataset used in the first step or different data entirely.

4. Train a new beat tracking network B_{AE} on

$$A_{\text{enc}}(X_1^{\text{train}}), A_{\text{enc}}(X_2^{\text{train}}), \dots, A_{\text{enc}}(X_N^{\text{train}}),$$

where $A_{\text{enc}}(X_i^{\text{train}})$ is the encoding of X_i^{train} using the trained autoencoder, with corresponding targets

$$\mathbf{y}_1^{\text{train}}, \mathbf{y}_2^{\text{train}}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N^{\text{train}}.$$

Note that we use the same set of hyperparameters as those used to train B_{Ref} .

5. Use this newly trained beat tracking system to calculate the new estimated BAFs

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_1^{\text{test}}, \hat{\mathbf{z}}_2^{\text{test}}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{z}}_N^{\text{test}}$$

from the encoded test set, where

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{\text{test}} = B_{\text{AE}} [A_{\text{enc}}(X_i^{\text{test}})]$$

6. Compare the BAFs produced by B_{AE} previous step with that of the BAF produced by the reference beat tracking system B_{Ref} .

Using this methodology, we can split the experiments that we perform into two categories.

1. Train the autoencoder on the same dataset as the reference beat tracking network, and experiment with the hyperparameters of the autoencoder.
2. Choose a set of hyperparameters that perform well from the previous step, and use them to train an autoencoder on increasingly large datasets, which are different to those used to train the beat tracking network.

The dataset that we use to train the beat tracking network is small, which will allow us to quickly train the autoencoder, create a new set of features, and train a

new beat tracking system on it. This fast training time allows us to quickly iterate through a set of hyperparameters to determine a good set.

The models described above have been implemented in the Python programming language [16] using the PyTorch machine learning framework [17], and trained using Google Colaboratory [18].

Chapter 4

Evaluation

We use this chapter to discuss the evaluation of the experiments we run, as well as the datasets used to train and evaluate them on.

4.1 F -measure

We begin by introducing terminology defined by Davies and Plumbley [19] in 2007.

Let

$$\gamma = (\gamma_b)_{b=1}^B$$

be a sequence of B estimated beat locations, and let

$$a = (a_j)_{j=1}^J$$

be the sequence of J annotated locations of the beats. We define the inter-beat-interval (IBI) as

$$\Delta_b = \gamma_b - \gamma_{b-1}$$

for $b = 2, \dots, B$, and the inter-annotation-interval (IAI) as

$$\Delta_j = a_j - a_{j-1}$$

for $j = 2, \dots, J$.

One metric used to evaluate the performance of classification algorithms is the F -measure. It was introduced for the evaluation of onset detection [20] and beat tracking [21] algorithms by Dixon.

Given a beat location γ_b , we say that the beat is correct if $|\gamma_b - a'| \leq \epsilon$, where a' is the annotation closest to γ_b , and ϵ is a tolerance given in milliseconds. Dixon took ϵ to be 50 milliseconds for onset detection, and 70 milliseconds for beat tracking. We say that a beat location γ_b is a false positive if $|\gamma_b - a'| > \epsilon$, and we say that a beat annotation a_j is a false negative if there exists no beat location γ_b such that $|\gamma_b - a_j| \leq \epsilon$ for $b \in B$.

We can then calculate the F -measure

$$F = \frac{2c}{2c + f^+ + f^-}$$

where c is the number of correct beat locations, f^+ is the number of false positives and f^- is the number of false negatives. We have that $F \in [0, 1]$, where $F = 1$ represents perfect accuracy, though we will express it as a percentage.

4.2 Continuity-based evaluation

This group of methods, described by Davies et al. [22], looks at a tolerance window around a beat and the previous beat to determine if it is correct.

Given an estimated beat location γ_b and its closest annotation a_j , we say that γ_b is correct if

1. $a_j - \theta\Delta_j < \gamma_b < a_j + \theta\Delta_j$,
2. $a_{j-1} - \theta\Delta_{j-1} < \gamma_{b-1} < a_{j-1} + \theta\Delta_{j-1}$, and
3. $(1 - \theta)\Delta_j < \Delta_b < (1 + \theta)\Delta_j$,

where θ is tolerance level, taken by Davies et al. to be 0.175.

We then cut the audio into M segments, and define Υ_m as the number of correct beats that lie within segment m , for $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$. Then we can define the proportion of beats at the correct metrical level with continuity required CML_c as

$$\text{CML}_c = \frac{\max(\Upsilon_m)}{J},$$

and the total number of correct beats at the correct metrical level CML_t as

$$\text{CML}_t = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M (\Upsilon_m)}{J}.$$

If we allow for the resampling of the annotations at double and half the correct metrical level, and if we allow for annotations that are off-beat, then we can define the allowed metrical level with continuity required AML_c , and the allowed metrical level with continuity not required AML_t . Like the F -measure, these will be expressed as a percentage.

4.3 Test Loss

Our beat tracking system outputs a BAF, not the locations of the beats. This BAF is passed to a dynamic programming algorithm which outputs the locations of the beats. As such, we use the test loss as a means to directly evaluate the output of the beat tracking system. The test loss is calculated using BCE loss function presented in equation (3.1), and is calculated using only the test set.

4.4 Datasets

We used two datasets to train and evaluate the models. These were the SMC Mirex beat tracking dataset and the Million Song Dataset (MSD).

In 2012, Holzapfel et al. [23] proposed a method of identifying music samples that are challenging for beat tracking algorithms. The method requires no ground truth and is based on selective sampling. From this, the authors then created a new dataset that proves difficult for beat tracking, which became known as the SMC

Mirex dataset. The dataset consists of 217 pieces of audio, each of which are 40 seconds in length and each with a corresponding text file containing the locations of beats, labelled by the authors.

The MSD was introduced in 2011 by Bertin-Mahieux et al. [24], and was an attempt to make a large, publicly available dataset for MIR research. The publicly available dataset consists of audio features and song metadata, but does not include the audio itself. However, we use the audio provided by the Music Technology Group to compute the features, as detailed in section 3.1.

We want to test the effect that using increasingly large datasets has on the performance of the autoencoder. To do this, we create subsets MSD_i of the MSD that double in size, where i is the number of songs in the dataset. We chose the sizes $i = 200, 400, 800, 1600, 3200$, and organised them into subsets

$$\text{MSD}_{200} \subset \text{MSD}_{400} \subset \text{MSD}_{800} \subset \text{MSD}_{1600} \subset \text{MSD}_{3200}.$$

To create subsets that are similar to the SMC Mirex dataset, we need to pick songs that are considered difficult to label. The MSD has beat labels for each song, and for each label has a beat confidence interval, a number between zero and one. For each song, we take the average of the beat confidence intervals and pick the 3200 songs with the smallest average beat confidence. Since there are many songs with an average beat confidence of zero, we randomly select the bottom 3200 songs.

Chapter 5

Results

In this section, we outline the experiments that we ran, including the datasets used for each and the hyperparameters varied. We also report and briefly discuss the results obtained for each experiment.

5.1 Reference beat tracking network

We began by running a set of experiments to choose the best hyperparameters for our reference beat tracking system. The beat tracking system was trained and tested on the SMC Mirex dataset. The hyperparameters we varied are listed below.

- The number of features H_S in the hidden state h_t of each LSTM unit, where h_t is shown in figure 3.
- The number of hidden layers H_L of each LSTM layer. That is, the number of stacked LSTM units in the layer.
- The linear size L_S , where $L_S = -1$ means that we are using no linear layer.
- The smoothing constant S_C used to smooth the BAF.
- The smoothing type S_T , which is either square or constant.

For all experiments throughout this chapter, we assign an experiment number E_i .

The first hyperparameters we experimented with were $H_S \in \{8, 16\}$ and $H_L \in \{1, 4\}$. The results of this are shown in table 1, where the train, test and validation loss are the loss values calculated when training the beat tracking network, not the autoencoder.

E_i	H_S	H_L	L_S	S_C	S_T	N_E	Train Loss	Validation Loss	Test Loss
1	8	4	-1	5	const	254	0.321	0.319	0.338
2	8	1	-1	5	const	312	0.335	0.325	0.342
3	16	4	-1	5	const	269	0.315	0.32	0.333
4	16	1	-1	5	const	471	0.329	0.322	0.339

Table 1: Varying H_S and H_L .

We then experimented with both the smoothing type and the number of hidden layers in each LSTM unit. The results are shown in table 2, and we see using square BAF smoothing leads to a significant loss in performance. From here on, we decided to use constant smoothing only.

E_i	H_S	H_L	L_S	S_C	S_T	N_E	Train Loss	Validation Loss	Test Loss
1	8	4	-1	5	const	254	0.321	0.319	0.338
2	8	1	-1	5	const	312	0.335	0.325	0.342
5	8	4	-1	5	square	343	0.57	0.601	0.626
6	8	1	-1	5	square	501	0.639	0.642	0.648

Table 2: Varying H_L and S_T .

The next set of experiments investigate the effect the linear size L_S has on performance. This is shown in table 3. One interesting point is that using no linear layer is better than using a linear layer with only 20 units.

E_i	H_S	H_L	L_S	S_C	S_T	N_E	Train Loss	Validation Loss	Test Loss
1	8	4	-1	5	const	254	0.321	0.319	0.338
7	8	4	20	5	const	666	0.297	0.315	0.344
8	8	4	50	5	const	283	0.319	0.32	0.337

Table 3: Varying L_S .

In the final batch of experiments, we experimented with the number of hidden layers, the linear size and the smoothing constant. As we are only using the constant

smoothing, S_C represents the number of frames either side of a beat location that are set to 1. This is shown in table 4 and we see that, interestingly, the biggest gain in performance is from setting the smoothing constant to 3.

E_i	H_S	H_L	L_S	S_C	S_T	N_E	Train Loss	Validation Loss	Test Loss
9	32	8	50	5	const	253	0.302	0.32	0.332
10	32	1	50	10	const	221	0.504	0.496	0.516
11	32	1	50	3	const	413	0.229	0.228	0.241
12	32	4	50	3	const	350	0.214	0.229	0.239
13	32	8	50	3	const	318	0.219	0.225	0.237
14	32	4	30	3	const	175	0.223	0.228	0.239
15	32	4	30	4	const	112	0.276	0.275	0.291

Table 4: Varying H_L , L_S and S_C .

Going forward, we decided to use the hyperparameters from experiment 13 for our reference beat tracking network. Since we do the rest of the experiments using five folds, we retrained the beat tracking network with these hyperparameters, and evaluated on one fold.

N_E	Train loss	Test loss	Validation loss
133	0.228	0.236	0.241

Table 5: The results of the reference beat tracking network.

5.2 Encoding size

Now that we have the reference beat tracking network defined, we can start training the autoencoder. The first experiment we run is to vary the size of the encoding, which is the output of the encoder A_{enc} . We test one overcomplete autoencoder where the size of the encoding is greater than the size of the input, and five under-complete autoencoders where the size of the encoder is smaller than the size of the input. The autoencoders are trained using the SMC Mirex dataset.

For this experiment, we vary the following hyperparameters.

- The encoding size S_{enc} .
- The linear encoder and decoder sizes S_{ED} .

The results of these experiments are shown in table 6, where N_{BTN} is the number of epochs required to train the beat tracking network and N_{AE} is the number of epochs required to train the autoencoder.

E_i	S_{enc}	S_{ED}	N_{AE}	N_{BTN}	Train loss	Test loss	Validation loss
1	4	64	29	30	0.258	0.26	0.273
2	8	64	32	30	0.245	0.249	0.258
3	16	64	19	36	0.248	0.251	0.262
4	32	64	27	50	0.241	0.246	0.252
5	64	96	45	40	0.241	0.245	0.252
6	128	120	46	41	0.24	0.244	0.251

Table 6: Varying S_{enc} .

The performance of the largest encoding size is the best, but as the difference is insignificant, and as it means training more parameters, we use an encoding size of 32 from now on.

5.3 Adding linear layers

For the following two experiments, we investigated the effects of adding more linear layers to the linear encoder and decoder. We added one linear layer with 32 nodes in the first experiment and two layers with 32 nodes each in the second experiment. The results are shown in table 7.

Linear Layers	N_{AE}	N_{BTN}	Train loss	Test loss	Validation loss
32	125	85	0.245	0.25	0.255
32,32	81	236	0.252	0.256	0.269

Table 7: Varying the number of linear layers.

We see that adding linear layers degrades performance, so from now on we do not add any linear layers.

5.4 Activation functions

Next, we experimented with three different activation functions in the linear layers. The linear layers in the autoencoders so far have been using the ReLU function defined in (2.2). The activation functions we test are the sigmoid function defined

in (2.1), the hyperbolic tangent function defined in (2.2), and the SELU function defined in (2.2). The results of this experiment are shown in table 8.

Activation	N_{AE}	N_{BTN}	Train Loss	Test loss	Validation loss
Sigmoid	118	108	0.237	0.244	0.249
tanh	180	134	0.24	0.25	0.25
SELU	186	170	0.238	0.244	0.25

Table 8: Varying the activation functions of linear layers.

5.5 Batch normalisation

The final experiment we do with the SMC Mirex dataset is to test the effectiveness of the batch normalisation layers in the autoencoder. To do this, we run one experiment where we have removed all of the batch normalisation layers in figure 6. The results of this experiment are shown in table 9. Given that it got the same results as the same experiment as in table 7, we remove the batch normalisation layers for the next set of experiments, as it adds more parameters to train, without adding any benefit.

N_{AE}	N_{BTN}	Train loss	Test loss	Validation loss
124	185	0.239	0.244	0.249

Table 9: Removing batch normalisation.

5.6 Training with large datasets

For the final set of experiments, we investigate the effect of training the autoencoder on increasingly large unlabelled datasets. To do this, we use the datasets calculated in section 4.4. We had hoped to use datasets of size 6400 and 12800 songs, but couldn't due to time restrictions. The results of these experiments are shown in table 10.

We see that the test loss decreased as we increased the size of the dataset, and in the case of the MSD_{3200} dataset, the test loss is almost on par with the reference beat tracking network.

Dataset size	N_{AE}	N_{BTN}	Train loss	Test loss	Validation loss
200	93	94	0.233	0.239	0.247
400	90	93	0.236	0.24	0.25
800	82	131	0.231	0.238	0.244
1600	114	372	0.23	0.239	0.246
3200	167	1394	0.23	0.237	0.244

Table 10: Varying the size of the dataset.

A plot of the results for these experiments is shown in figure 7, where we see an obvious downward trend in the value of the test loss.

Figure 7: A plot showing how the test loss changes with the size of the dataset.

Since we are seeing similar performance now for the test loss, it is worth using some more typical beat tracking evaluation metrics. In table 11, we list some of the results of the F -measure and the continuity based evaluation methods described in chapter 4, where the results have all been calculated on the output of beat tracking network for the test set.

The results in table 11 are all expressed in percentages, and we can see a slight improvement in performance over the reference beat tracking network. For the F -measure, we see that the reference beat tracking network is outperformed by the

Experiment	F -measure	CML _c	CML _t	AML _c	AML _t
200	31.56	18.47	27.71	29.81	44.23
400	31.78	16.05	25.37	26.89	42.8
800	31.45	18.26	28.12	31.55	48.55
1600	34.21	17.33	27.92	29.49	45.32
3200	33.09	20.28	30.97	30.34	45.91
Ref	32.67	12.97	20.4	25.15	40.93

Table 11: F -measure and continuity based evaluation metrics calculated on the output of the models using the test set.

other systems when trained on 1600 and 3200 songs. For the continuity based evaluation, however, we see that the reference beat tracking system is outperformed by all of the systems trained on the MSD subsets, which is surprising given the small difference in test losses observed.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this final chapter, we discuss the results achieved, list the contributions of the thesis and propose future areas of work.

6.1 Discussion

Throughout the course of this thesis, we were limited by time available and the size of the models we could run. This was partly due to the time limited nature of a thesis, but also due to time and memory limits in Google Colaboratory. If we had more time and greater resources available, it would have been possible to run more extensive experiments with larger models. In particular, it would have been interesting to train deeper autoencoders using subsets of the MSD larger than 3200 songs. Despite this, we believe we have shown the potential of autoencoders to improve the state of the art, and that they warrant further research.

We summarise the contributions of this thesis below.

1. We proposed an autoencoder architecture for beat tracking.
2. We evaluated the performance of the autoencoder when trained on the same data as model
3. We evaluated the effect of using large, unlabelled datasets.

6.2 Future work

During the experiments, we trained the beat tracking system on the output of the trained encoder, but a possible improvement might be to train the autoencoder on a large set of unlabelled data, then attach the encoder to the input of the beat tracking system, using the trained weights as the initial weights for the encoder. This should allow for some fine tuning of the weights learned from the unsupervised learning task.

Given that autoencoders try to perform feature fusion on the inputs, it's possible that using the Mel spectrograms is inhibiting training. Instead, it could be beneficial to train the autoencoder directly on the magnitude spectrum, using a deeper autoencoder to learn a good representation. Further, it could be beneficial to train an autoencoder using a mixture of convolutional and LSTM layers, rather than just LSTM layers.

A simpler area of research could be to train deeper versions of our proposed architecture, and to take advantage of larger datasets during the training of the autoencoder. We were only able to train the autoencoder using 3200 songs, but it would be interesting to see the asymptotic relation between the size of the dataset and the test loss.

List of Figures

1	A rolled RNN.	5
2	An unrolled RNN.	5
3	The insides of an LSTM node.	6
4	All autoencoders have a similar structure.	8
5	The structure of the beat tracking network used.	20
6	The structure of the autoencoder used.	21
7	A plot showing how the test loss changes with the size of the dataset.	33

List of Tables

1	Varying H_S and H_L	29
2	Varying H_L and S_T	29
3	Varying L_S	29
4	Varying H_L , L_S and S_C	30
5	The results of the reference beat tracking network.	30
6	Varying S_{enc}	31
7	Varying the number of linear layers.	31
8	Varying the activation functions of linear layers.	32
9	Removing batch normalisation.	32
10	Varying the size of the dataset.	33
11	F -measure and continuity based evaluation metrics calculated on the output of the models using the test set.	34

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